

Metal Complexes as Ligands. Polynuclear Alkali Metal Complexes with Diaquomonooxalato-nickel(II) and -cobalt(II)

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Polymeric octahedral, diaquomonooxalato-nickel(II) and -cobalt(II) [Ni/Co(ox).2H₂O] have been used as 'metal complex ligands' in the synthesis of oxygen-bridged binuclear alkali metal complexes of the general formula [(M_bL).M_aox.2H₂O], where M_b=Li, Na and K; L=deprotonated organic acids; M_a=Ni or Co; and ox=oxalate. In these binuclear alkali metal transition metal oxalates, the C=O frequencies have been observed only below 1 650 cm⁻¹ suggesting that all the oxalato groups present in the Ni/Co adducts are not normal/terminal ones; most likely they are bridged ones. The electronic spectral and magnetic moment studies indicate that the polymerised octahedral Ni^{II} and Co^{II} ions are converted into tetrahedral ones in their alkali metal adducts.

OXYGEN bridged metal complexes, using 'metal complexes as ligands', have now become of interest to coordination chemists. Schiff bases¹⁻⁴ and β-diketones⁵ have been used to synthesise polynuclear complexes.

It has been observed that these dimeric¹⁻⁴, trimeric, tetrameric⁵ and polymeric⁶ metal complexes most likely depolymerise in presence of alkali metal salts in non-aqueous medium; and then the monomers act as Lewis bases, and form stable compounds with suitable Lewis acids. After breaking the metal-oxygen bond of the polymer, the oxygen atoms *in situ*, are now left with further coordinative power, and form oxygen bridged polynuclear complexes⁷⁻⁹. In the process, the geometry of the central atom of the metal complexes (with higher coordination number, usually six), change in the 'metal complexes as ligand' (lower coordination number, usually four). Felthouse *et al.*⁷ have reported that in [Cu₂(Et₂dien)₂C₂O₄] the oxalate dianion bridges in a bis-bidentate fashion the two distorted trigonal bipyramidal copper centres.

We have selected polymeric octahedral diaquomonooxalato-nickel(II), and -cobalt(II) [Ni/Co(ox).(H₂O)₂] as 'metal complex ligands', and have extended the studies on oxygen-bridged complexes, by synthesising a number of stable hetero-binuclear alkali metal mixed ligand complexes of the general formula [M_bL.₂{M_a(ox)(H₂O)₂}], where M_a=Ni^{II} and Co^{II}; M_b=Li, Na and K; and L=deprotonated 8-hydroxyquinoline and 1-nitroso-2-naphthol.

Results and Discussion

Analytical data (Table 1) showed that one molecule of lithium, sodium and potassium salts of organic acids, combined with one molecule of the transition metal oxalates. The usual method of synthesis was to take metal oxalate in absolute

ethanol and add alkali metal salts to it, usually in the molar ratio of 1 : 1. The mixture was refluxed for 2-3 h on a hot-plate with constant stirring, whereby a clear solution was obtained and the adducts were precipitated in cold condition. The colour of the adducts have been found to be quite different from that of the 'complex ligands', and their decomposition temperatures have also been found to be higher than that of the corresponding 'complex ligands'. The adducts are stable under dried condition but decompose on exposure to moisture.

Infrared spectra: Absorption in the ir attributable to C=O stretching vibration normally occurs in the region of 1 700-1 750 cm⁻¹ for the esters of carboxylic acids and in the region 1 600-1 650 cm⁻¹ for their salts; a clear distinction being observed between carboxyl groups linked to neighbouring atoms by covalency and ionic bonds.

Polymeric Ni(ox).2H₂O and Co(ox).2H₂O were reported to have linear chain structures isomorphous with Fe(ox).2H₂O⁸. Recent crystal structure determination for Ni(ox).2H₂O⁹ shows a three-dimensional polymeric network of octahedrally coordinated Ni^{II}. The central metal ion has been found to be six coordinated; each Ni^{II} ion is surrounded by four oxygen atoms of bridging oxalate groups and the fifth and sixth positions are occupied by two water molecules. All the oxalate groups are bridging ones.

In case of trivalent metal oxalates and also the oxalates of Pt^{III}, Pd^{III} and Be^{III}, the observed ν_{C=O}¹⁰ is above 1 700 cm⁻¹ (Table 2) which suggested a truly covalent metal-oxygen bonding. Nakamoto¹¹ has also mentioned the ester ν_{C=O} at 1 760 cm⁻¹. In polymeric Ni^{II}, Co^{II} and Fe^{II} oxalato complexes, none of the C=O groups are free, like the trivalent oxalato-metal complexes. The C=O groups are strongly attached through coordi-

TABLE 1

Compd.	Colour	Decomp. Temp. °C	$\nu_{C=O}$ cm^{-1}	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			Magnetic moment B.M.
				Ni/Co	N	Na/K	
Ni(ox).2H ₂ O≡L	Sky blue	290 (250t)	1 620	—	—	—	3.40
Li1N2N.L	Brownish yellow	295	1 620	16.8 (16.0)	3.80 (3.87)	—	3.68
Na1N2N.L	Brownish yellow	310	1 610	15.5 (15.3)	3.9 (3.7)	6.3 (6.1)	3.62
K1N2N.L	Light brown	305	1 620	13.9 (14.7)	3.1 (3.5)	10.2 (9.9)	3.60
Li8HQ.L	Light brown	330	1 630	18.6 (17.4)	4.2 (4.2)	—	3.50
Na8HQ.L	Greenish yellow	325	1 630	16.8 (16.6)	4.1 (4.0)	7.05 (6.59)	3.65
K8HQ.L	Greenish yellow	335	1 640	16.3 (15.8)	3.85 (3.80)	10.9 (10.6)	3.58
Co(ox).2H ₂ O≡L'	Pink	295 (260t)	1 620	—	—	—	5.20
Li1N2N.L'	Reddish brown	305	—	17.0 (16.2)	3.90 (3.86)	—	4.85
Na1N2N.L'	Reddish brown	310	1 630	16.3 (15.6)	3.6 (3.7)	5.9 (6.0)	4.90
K1N2N.L'	Reddish brown	300	1 620	15.2 (14.3)	3.55 (3.55)	10.10 (9.89)	4.85
Li8HQ.L'	Greenish yellow	300	—	18.1 (17.6)	3.80 (4.13)	—	4.85
Na8HQ.L'	Greenish yellow	310	1 620	18.1 (16.8)	4.0 (4.0)	7.00 (6.57)	4.90
K8HQ.L'	Yellowish green	305	1 610 (1 670 sh)	17.29 (16.12)	3.9 (3.8)	11.2 (10.6)	—

TABLE 2—OXALATO COMPLEXES OF BI- AND TRI-VALENT METALS

Metals	$\nu_{C=O}$ cm^{-1}	
Fe ^{III} (Monomer)	1 712	(Free/terminal)
Co ^{III} (Monomer)	1 707	(Free/terminal)
Pd ^{II} (Monomer)	1 698	(Free/terminal)
Mn ^{II} (Polymer)	1 635	(Bridged)
Ni ^{II} (Polymer)	1 635	(Bridged)
Co ^{II} (Polymer)	1 625	(Bridged)
Fe ^{II} (Polymer)	1 620	(Bridged)

nate bonding to different metal ions. As a result, the $\nu_{C=O}$ values show up at a lower ($\sim 1\ 635\ cm^{-1}$) frequency (Table 2). Previously these low values categorised them to be ionic oxalates. However, now it can be generalised that for covalently bonded oxalate groups, when the C=O groups are free (terminal ones), the frequencies are usually above $1\ 700\ cm^{-1}$; whereas, when it is in a polymer with oxalato bridges, the $\nu_{C=O}$ are below $1\ 650\ cm^{-1}$. The single bonded C—C structure of polymeric oxalates, has been suggested^{1,2}.

In these binuclear alkali metal-transition metal oxalates, the $\nu_{C=O}$ have been observed below $1\ 650\ cm^{-1}$, invariably between $1\ 630$ and $1\ 600\ cm^{-1}$. So it is quite apparent that all the oxalate groups present in Ni/Co adducts, are not normal/terminal ones; most likely they are bridged ones, bridging the transition metals with alkali metals.

The sharp O—H stretching frequencies at $3\ 350$ – $3\ 375\ cm^{-1}$, together with rocking δ_{H_2O} at 830 – $840\ cm^{-1}$ suggest that the two water molecules are coordinated in the adducts, similar to the metal complexes.

Magnetic properties : The magnetic moment of Ni(ox).2H₂O is 3.4 B.M., but in the adducts they are high, between 3.5–3.7 B.M. (Table 1). The magnetic moment of Co(ox).2H₂O is 5.2 B.M., but in its adducts they are lower, between 4.8–4.9 B.M.

Electronic spectra : The visible spectrum of Ni(ox).2H₂O shows typical octahedral spectrum of Ni^{II}, with three absorption bands at 380, 620 and 1 150 nm. The spectrum of alkali metal adducts have been different from that of the 'complex ligand' and show only one absorption at ~ 650 nm. Co(ox).2H₂O shows only one absorption at 500 nm, characteristic of an octahedral Co^{II} complex. The alkali metal adducts also show only one absorption which appears at ~ 600 nm.

Structure and bonding : The magnetic and electronic spectral studies reveal that the octahedral Ni^{II} and Co^{II} ions in the polymeric M(ox)(H₂O)₂ are converted into tetrahedral ones in their alkali metal adducts. The bonding between metal oxalates and the alkali metal salts are most likely through oxygen atoms of carbonyl groups. This has been supported by ir spectra (showing bridging oxalato groups), magnetic moments and electronic spectral studies (showing tetrahedral stereochemistry) of the adducts. The two water molecules are coordinated to the metal ion of the 'complex ligand'. The

probable structure and bonding of the newly prepared adducts of the general formula $[M_a(ox).2H_2O]M_bL$ is shown below.

where, $M_a = Ni^{II}$ and Co^{II} ; $M_b = Li, Na$ and K ; and $L =$ deprotonated 8HQ and 1N2N.

That the oxalate ion is attached to M_b , and L to M_a and not to M_b , have been inferred as follows: (i) there is no replacement reaction when 1N2N/8HQ is reacted with $M_b(ox).2H_2O$ in absolute ethanol, and (ii) the adduct $M_aL.M_b(ox).2H_2O$ when treated with water or when boiled for a long time with absolute ethanol, resulted in the regeneration of the metal complex ligand $M_b(ox).2H_2O$.

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